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Research Article

A CASE STUDY TO DETERMINE THE PURPOSE OF UTILISATION, AND PREFERENCE OF OF ORTHOPANTOMOGRAM (OPG) AS COMPARED TO CONE BEAM COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY (CBCT) BY DENTAL PRACTITIONERS AND ORAL RADIOLOGISTS.

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Background: In the field of dentistry, Cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) has become an authentic tool for both diagnosis and treatment planning. Advantages of CBCT are numerous over 2D imaging techniques (OPG). Trend of preference and purpose of utilisation of these imaging modalities by equal dental practitioners and oral radiologists should be evaluated.

Purpose and preference of utilisation of CBCT and OPG by various dental practitioners in their clinical practice, its evaluation was the cause of this study.

Materials/Methods: With the consent of referring dentist, patient and ethical committee of CMH medical college and Allied hospital Faisalabad, CBCT and OPG data of 630 different cases treated by different Dental practitioners and Oral radiologists in Lahore and Faisalabad was subjected to cross sectional study, as the study included both the centers. Mann-Whitney U test (Z test) was used for comparison.

Results: OPG was more commonly ordered by general dentists (31%) followed by prosthodontists (30%), and CBCT was advised by general dental practitioner (25%) followed by OMFS (23%)

For fixed partial denture planning (FPD), OPG preference was greater i.e. 59%, for implant planning CBCT was highly preferred i.e. 61%

Conclusion: According to present studies, CBCT was advocated for implant planning, OPG was advocated for FPD planning, general dentists and oral radiologists preferred OPG and CBCT compared to the other dental practitioners. Furthermore, increase in the preference of CBCT over OPG had been seen.

Mesh keywords: Cone-Beam Computed Tomography – Imaging, Three-dimensional – Radiography, Panoramic.

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INTRODUCTION:

Fifteen years ago as an adaptive technology to meet the demand for three-dimensional (3D) information regarding craniofacial imaging, Cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) scanners were introduced. To analyse the purpose

of utilisation and preference of CBCT and OPG by Dental Practitioners, with the consent of referring dentist, patient and ethical committee of CMH medical college and Allied hospital Faisalabad, as the study included both the centers.

FIGURE1. Contribution of OPG and CBCT data.

(OPG=64,CBCT=556)630 cases were studied as sample.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The data base of 630 CBCT and OPG examinations were performed and the data was collected with the consent of referring dentist, patient and ethical committee of CMH medical college and Allied hospital Faisalabad, as the study included both the centres.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

Patients undergoing digital imaging who gave consent for the study were included in our study.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

Patients who did not give consent for the study were not included in our study.

RESULTS:

CBCT constituted 89.8% (556) while OPG 10.2% (64) of all examinations, out of 630 cases. (Figure 1)

Following percentages of different dental practitioners who advised OPG (N=64) were ascertained by the analyzed data.

General dentist, 30% (19), prosthodontists, 29% (18), OMFS, 14% (8), orthodontist, 8% (6), periodontists, 8% (6), endodontist, 7% (4) and pedodontist, 4% (2). (Figure 2)

Dental practitioners who advised CBCT (N=556) according to the analyzed data: general dentist comprised 26% (54), OMFS 24% (130), prosthodontist, 18.4% (103), orthodontist 11.4% (63), endodontist 10% (54), periodontist 6.4% (36), oral radiologist 3.4% (19) and pedodontist 2% (11) (Figure 3)

Among the 10.2% (N=64) of cases referred for OPG, the reason for OPG was FPD planning, 58% (33), periodontists, 2% (1), impactions, 10% (6), orthodontic treatment planning, 4% (3), jaw fractures, 2% (2), root canal planning, 3% (2) and pre-implant planning, 25% (14) (Figure 4)

Figure 2. dental practitioners who orders OPG(percentage)

Figure3.Different dental practioner who ordered CBCT

Among the 89.8% (N=556) OF CASES referred for CBCT, the purpose of CBCT was pre-implant,41%(234),post-implant planning, 20%(112), impactions 14%(85),root canal planning11%(56),orthodontic treatment planning,4%(24),cysts,5%(17),jaw fractures 1%(10)periodontist,3%(13)(Figure5)

A value of(<0.04)p was obtained statistically which showed that CBCT was preferred implant planning(pre-implant planning,post-implant planning) which is followed by other reasons that include periodontist,jaw fractures, cyst,orthodontic treatment planning and root canal treatment planning.For FPD planning and

bone evaluation in periodontist,OPG was preferred(TABLE1)

DISCUSSION:

In recent times,number of dentist who prefer digital radiography over conventional film radiography has increased.Purpose and preference of 3-D imaging(CBCT) compare to orthopantomogram(OPG) by dental practitioner in their clinical practice was the main focus of our study so in order to evaluate the above mentioned aspects,this study was performed.According to our study,10.2%(N=64)of dentist who ordered OPG for both diagnosis and treatment.

Figure 4. Different reasons for using OPG, in percentages.Sample of 64 cases where OPG was advised

Figure 5.556 cases where CBCT was advised were taken as a sample. Different reasons for using CBCT, in percentages

Table 1.

Preferential use of OPG and CBCT in different

OPG vs. CBCT	Z value	P value	CBCT
Cyst	4.11	<.004	✓
FPD planning	-5.66	>.04	×
Impaction+implant	5.9	<.004	✓
Impactions	6.88	<.004	✓
Jaw fracture	3.73	<.004	✓
Ortho planning	3.79	>.04	✓
Periodontitis	-0.81	<.004	×
Post implant	10.53	<.004	✓
Pre implant	14.93	<.004	✓
Root canal planning	7.33	<.004	✓

89.8% of dentists ordered CBCT, according to our study, and it shows that the use of CBCT is famous among practitioners.

According to recent studies, OPG was advocated mainly for FPD planning. 545 dental practitioners confessed that OPG is a helpful tool for multiple carious lesions and endodontics.

In different fields of dentistry ,dental practitioners have a fair idea. Due to its advantage over conventional imaging systems,it is preferred in implant planning.it can be because of its ability of 3-D reconstructions in craniofacial region.

An excellent general overview of the dentition is provided by OPG.however,when used for pre- and post-implant assessment,it has certain limits.that includes,magnification in the vertical plane and the image is a two-dimensional representation of a three-dimensional entity.that is why practitioners are using 3D imaging over 2D OPG.the 3D imaging allows the practitioners to do better diagnosis of the disease so they can do a better treatment .

CONCLUSION:

In the field of dentistry,cone beam computed tomography is relatively advanced imaging technique with a profound potential, dental professionals are also realizing and accepting this fact.This technique is most advanced and globally accepted.To accurately treat oral and maxillofacial diseases ,dental specialists should become more familiar with various CBCT machines,as oral radiologists are , and with appropriate softwares and interpretations.

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